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CONTRIBUTION TO THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

In this paper, a studious analysis will present new opportunities for the application of artificial intelligence in the project management process, perspectives will be presented on how it could contribute to improving efficiency and effectiveness in managing IT projects by using sophisticated analytical methods, process automation, predictive models and the application of methods, techniques and tools of business intelligence. Although practice research shows that more than 75 percent of projects end in failure or exceed deadlines, costs, etc., there is still not a sufficient number of scientific and professional studies on this topic. The fundamental goal of this paper is to examine the process of managing IT projects related to artificial intelligence and assessing the possible impact, defining the strengths and weaknesses of using artificial intelligence in project management. The main purpose of this research is to objectively compare the strengths and weaknesses of methods, techniques and tools for project management and to identify the best practices and useful aspects that could be used by small and medium-sized enterprises and business systems in Kosovo and Metohija and the surrounding area when choosing the most suitable software tool for their specific needs of the project management process. The methodology of a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of scientific research will be applied in the paper. The results of the research will provide a better understanding of the possible effects of artificial intelligence on the process of project management and implementation, and support and facilitate the business decision-making process of company management in the acquisition and selection of methods, techniques, and concrete software tools for project management processes.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, project management, software implementation

PRILOG PRIMENI VEŠTAČKE INTELEGENCIJE U UPRAVLJANJU PROJEKTIMA

Apstrakt

U ovom radu, studiozna analiza će predstaviti nove mogućnosti za primenu veštačke inteligencije u procesu upravljanja projektima, biće predstavljene perspektive o tome kako bi ona mogla doprineti poboljšanju efikasnosti i efektivnosti u upravljanju IT projektima korišćenjem sofisticiranih analitičkih metoda, automatizacije procesa, prediktivnih modela i primenom metoda, tehnika i alata poslovne inteligencije. Iako istraživanja prakse pokazuju da više od 75 odsto projekata završava neuspehom ili prekoračenjem rokova, troškova itd., još uvek nema dovoljan broj naučnih i stručnih radova na ovu temu. Osnovni cilj rada je zasnovan na procesu upravljanja IT projektima vezanim za veštačku inteligenciju i proceni mogućeg uticaja, definisanju prednosti i slabosti korišćenja veštačke inteligencije u upravljanju projektima. Glavni cilj ovog istraživanja je objektivno upoređivanje prednosti i slabosti metoda, tehnika i alata za upravljanje projektima i identifikovanje najboljih praksi i korisnih aspekata koje bi mala i srednja preduzeća i poslovni sistemi na Kosovu i Metohiji i u okolini mogli da koriste prilikom izbora najprikladnijeg softverskog alata za svoje specifične potrebe procesa upravljanja projektima. U radu će biti primenjena metodologija kombinacije kvalitativnih i kvantitativnih metoda naučnog istraživanja. Rezultati istraživanja će pružiti bolje razumevanje mogućih efekata veštačke inteligencije na proces upravljanja projektima i njihove implementacije i podržati i olakšati proces donošenja poslovnih odluka menadžmenta kompanije u nabavci i izboru metoda, tehnika i konkretnih softverskih alata za procese upravljanja projektima.

Ključne reči: Veštačka inteligencija, upravljanje projektima, implementacija softvera

INTRODUCTION

It is known that artificial intelligence represents an interdisciplinary concept that explores the possibilities of creating machines capable of communicating with the environment and acting based on received data in a way that is considered intelligent (Denić, 2024). In this context, the understanding of artificial intelligence goes beyond just programming or the study of the brain, as it includes complex research in areas such as search and inference, knowledge representation and uncertainty processing, machine learning, natural language processing, speech and vision recognition, as well as robotics (Ryu and Han, 2018). It is important to emphasize that it is extremely efficient and effective in making data-based decisions and performing repetitive or computer-driven tasks (Glover, 2024). The same author further points out that artificial intelligence helps protect people by piloting online fraud detection systems and robots for dangerous jobs (Glover, 2024). Well-known authors state that the goal of artificial intelligence is to enable machines to imitate human thoughts and behaviors, including learning, thinking, predicting, etc. (Xu, et al., 2021), which represents a high use value for many aspects of different fields, including marketing, which represents one of the most important areas of application of artificial intelligence.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In general, it can be said that artificial intelligence represents a machine imitation of human cognitive processes that uses computer systems, natural language processing, speech recognition and machine vision (Chatterjee, 2020, p. 13). In this regard, Emmert-Streib, Yli-Harja and Dehmer (2020) conclude that artificial intelligence is an attempt to create some kind of intelligence that is not natural. The modern definition of artificial intelligence includes computers that perform cognitive tasks characteristic of the human mind, such as learning and problem solving, and includes technologies such as machine learning and natural language processing (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Some authors emphasize that it differs from the natural intelligence possessed by humans and animals (Chatterjee, 2020, p. 13). In the processes of artificial intelligence, large data sets can be processed so-called. deep learning to identify subtle patterns and correlations that can provide companies with a competitive advantage (Tucci, 2024). The development of technologies and specifically progress in hardware and access to large amounts of data and advanced algorithms have enabled the exponential growth and development of artificial intelligence, which today is an integral part of many technologies and services we use every day (Denić, 2015). Some authors state that artificial intelligence, whose beginnings date back to the 1960s in the 20th century, has experienced enormous development in recent years (Das, 2021, p. 7). In the literature, two categories of artificial intelligence are mainly highlighted: weak artificial intelligence and strong artificial intelligence. In this context, we distinguish between strong artificial intelligence, which imitates human thinking and behavior, and weak artificial intelligence, which is limited to specific functions and cannot independently think or solve problems (Ryu and Han, 2018). Chronologically, some authors state that artificial intelligence systems are the result of advances in the basic concepts of artificial intelligence, including machine learning, neural networks, natural language processing, and computer vision. (Coursiera org. 2024). The following image shows the typical areas of artificial intelligence.

Figure 1 AREAS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Source: Lateef, 2021

Research shows that in recent years the concept of strong artificial intelligence has been significantly transformed and is increasingly being referred to as general artificial intelligence, which does not mean only machines, but also the simulation of human thinking and learning about the world around them, as humans do (Emmert-Streib et al., 2020).

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project management has developed over the centuries, and with the advancement of technology and changes in the business world, the tools used for effective project management have also changed (Denić, 2014). The IT project is an important driver of change in society, which can be reflected in the field of information technology (Markus, 2014). Today, many companies and business systems decide to purchase software tools for project management purposes without a detailed and systematic consideration of their specific needs and requirements (Crawford, 2011). According to Schwalbe (2010, pp. 406, 433), many experts agree that one of the biggest threats to project management failure is unclear communication. Some authors like (Caniëls and Bakens, 2011) point out that IT project management supports the decision-making process at all levels of the organization, especially in planning, organizing and controlling the project in independent complex projects as well as in a multi-project environment. In this context, the well-known authors Moszkiewicz and Rostek (2011) mention other important features of IT project management processes and systems, especially in relation to data management, such as knowledge retention, standardized data record, data confidentiality (data access management), data integrity (relevance, completeness, accuracy, topicality), data availability (data available on request), easier data search, ensuring data durability (storage). They emphasize that the project information system is very important in terms of storing and organizing knowledge from past projects, which also serves to prepare for new projects. It is common knowledge that no tool is and cannot be perfect, but it is important to take into account that in the decision-making process the decision itself depends primarily on the nature of business systems and companies, their needs, the type of projects, current processes and tools, and last but not least, on the culture and policy of the company (McCormick, 2012). In this context, the well-known author emphasizes that due to the complexity and importance of many IT projects, it is important to evaluate the project at each stage and that it be in accordance with the realization of the planned activities and in accordance with the set goal (Schwalbe, 2010, pp. 62-73).

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE PROJECT MANAGEMENT PROCESS

By using artificial intelligence, companies can improve the efficiency of their business processes, increase productivity and profitability, but the value of artificial intelligence is not only in the technology of the systems themselves, but in how

companies use these systems to help people (Denić, 2015). Project management and artificial intelligence are closely related in the modern business world because artificial intelligence is revolutionizing the way projects are planned, implemented, and monitored. Project management tools are software solutions that play a key role in successful project management in modern organizations (Denić, 2024). They enable effective planning, organization, and monitoring of projects, including goal setting, task allocation, and resource management. There are many different project management tools designed to help plan, organize, and track projects. More well-known project management tools include web, desktop and mobile tools (Vujović, 2020). Web-based project management tools are available through a web browser, allowing users to access project information from a variety of devices, including smartphones and tablets, and have become very popular due to their accessibility and flexibility. Each tool contains its main functionalities, and what is characteristic in today's time is that these tools are supported by artificial intelligence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This scientific research is based on the author's many years of research work and theoretical knowledge, acquired during studies, many years of studying domestic and, above all foreign scholarly work, as well as on practical experiences of studying and monitoring the implementation of artificial intelligence in business with an emphasis on project management processes. The research methods are based on analysis and observation, presentation, and evaluation of the theoretical and practical aspects of the analysis of the practical application of artificial intelligence in project management processes.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Research indicates that businesses should find the right AI methods, techniques, and tools based on their needs, as the right AI tool helps them save costs and improve their business results. Web tools, supported by artificial intelligence, bring a wide range of functionalities that enable more efficient planning, management, and implementation of projects. For example, with the help of artificial intelligence, project managers can more accurately predict potential problems or risks, optimize the allocation of resources, and adjust strategies in a timely manner based on the analysis of real data. Practice shows that project management tools are designed to facilitate every aspect of project management, from initial planning to final realization and analysis. The latest results and predictions indicating that artificial intelligence will take over 80% of the tasks of project managers by 2030 have raised concerns that it could completely replace human managers. In this context, it can be said that these tools are crucial for optimizing project management and achieving the desired results. Research indicates that, according to the CHAOS Manifesto (2013), only 39 percent of software development projects are successful, i.e., completed on

time, within budget, and provided with all the functionality they provide. In this direction, the following 43 percent of projects are disputed, i.e., completed and operational, exceeding the budget, deadline, and with less functionality than originally planned. In the end, the remaining 18 percent of projects were unsuccessful; that is, they were prematurely terminated or suspended, or the software was never used. In this sense, we still have worrying results from the practice of project management and the introduction of IT in business. Only 10 percent of information systems development projects are successful, 52 percent are challenged, and 38 percent are unsuccessful. In a survey conducted in 22 organizations, 24% answered yes, 34% did not know, and 42% answered that it is not used, which means that artificial intelligence is used in almost a quarter of the surveyed companies and business systems.

Graph 1

Application of artificial intelligence in the company

Source: Authors' calculations

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Research results indicate that AI-powered project management tools enable the automation of routine tasks, allowing managers to focus on strategic aspects of projects, such as communicating with key stakeholders and aligning goals. It is known that about 24% of companies and business systems have adopted artificial intelligence, which represents a new possibility of business improvement through greater automation for many companies and organizations in the future (Denić, 2013). Eminent experts emphasize that one of the key conditions for the success of artificial intelligence and IT projects is investment in education to retrain people for new jobs (Thomas, 2024). Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that choosing the right tool for project management requires a thorough analysis of functionality, performance, and user needs, which is crucial for successful project management and the achievement of set goals. Based on the review of the literature and the analysis of business cases of the application of artificial intelligence, it can be concluded that among the key disadvantages of artificial intelligence are limitations in the areas of creativity, emotional intelligence, and ethics, which can affect the way technology affects society. In this context, the research results of certain authors indicate that business leaders or company managers can use current insights to make effective business decisions (Thomas, 2024). In this sense, it is important to emphasize that in society, however, there is a growing dependence on artificial

intelligence and issues related to privacy, security, and the impact on employment - all of this represents additional challenges that require careful consideration, studious analysis, and resolution.

CONCLUSION

The results of the literature review and research conducted in practice indicate that artificial intelligence brings many benefits to project management. Considering the topicality of the topic and the increasingly massive application of artificial intelligence, there is still not enough relevant literature, that is, there is very little available that would closely link the use of artificial intelligence and IT project management. Based on the analysis, it can be said that in addition to the basic advantages, the additional value of the application of artificial intelligence is represented by functionalities such as automatic report generation, advanced data analysis and optimization, as well as precision and speed in task management. However, in addition to the fact that research shows that artificial intelligence is an excellent tool, numerous studies show that companies and business systems can use it in the wrong way, which can cause an increase in company costs, that is, cause business damage. The research results indicate that today, there are software tools on the market that follow a certain concept or offer certain functionalities that can help in the more efficient management of IT projects. The connection between the project manager and artificial intelligence is that the artificial intelligence accurately analyzes the data, while the project manager uses that information to make strategic decisions and manage complex situations. The collected data showed that artificial intelligence is present to a certain extent in business systems and companies in the Republic of Serbia. On the basis of the above, it can be concluded that artificial intelligence will not replace the human ability to manage projects in due time, but complements it and strengthens the role of project managers.

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REZIME

U ovom radu se sprovodi studiozna analiza potencijala primene veštačke inteligencije (VI) u savremenom upravljanju projektima, sa posebnim fokusom na IT projekte. Rad istražuje na koje načine VI može doprineti unapređenju efikasnosti i efektivnosti u upravljanju projektima kroz primenu sofisticiranih analitičkih metoda, automatizaciju procesa, upotrebu prediktivnih modela, kao i integraciju metoda, tehnika i alata poslovne inteligencije. U kontekstu sve veće složenosti i dinamike IT projekata, kao i zabrinjavajućih podataka iz prakse prema kojima više od 75% projekata ne uspeva da se realizuje u predviđenim rokovima, budžetima ili u skladu sa početnim ciljevima, analiza u ovom radu postaje posebno relevantna. Iako praksa pokazuje jasnu potrebu za inovacijama u projekt menadžmentu, naučna i stručna literatura o primeni veštačke inteligencije u ovoj oblasti još uvek je relativno oskudna. Osnovni cilj ovog istraživanja jeste da pruži objektivnu procenu mogućeg uticaja VI na proces upravljanja IT projektima, kao i da identifikuje konkretne prednosti i ograničenja ovakvog pristupa. Poseban akcenat stavljen je na mala i srednja preduzeća i poslovne sisteme sa teritorije Kosova i Metohije i okoline, s ciljem da se ponude preporuke za izbor najprikladnijih softverskih rešenja u skladu sa njihovim specifičnim potrebama. U metodološkom smislu, rad se oslanja na kombinaciju kvalitativnih i kvantitativnih istraživačkih metoda, uključujući analizu slučaja, anketna ispitivanja, intervju sa ekspertima i evaluaciju postojećih alata. Rezultati istraživanja pružiće dublje razumevanje potencijala i izazova koje donosi integracija VI u projektni menadžment, a dobijeni

nalazi mogu služiti kao osnova za donošenje informisanih odluka menadžmenta u vezi sa izborom i implementacijom odgovarajućih tehnologija i metodologija. Na taj način, rad ima i praktičan doprinos unapređenju konkurentnosti malih i srednjih preduzeća kroz tehnološku modernizaciju procesa upravljanja projektima.